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Homogenous nation states and regions of diversity. State building and formulaic sequences.

Abstract

The notion of ‘formulaic language’ in terms of analytical tool appears relevant from a historical perspective, e.g. with respect to early-modern state building. Centralization of political power and homogeneity of legal and other institutional arrangements – two key features of the modern state – was preceded by or, as in some cases, went hand in hand with conceptual innovation, linguistic standardization, and new ways to talk and write about politics and statesmanship in diplomatic and legal context. For example, the two, emerging Nordic states – Denmark and Sweden – are cases in point. However, neither Denmark nor Sweden were homogenous entities from an ethnic and cultural point of view. Denmark enclosed both what would eventually (re-)emerge as independent Norway, as well as substantial parts of what today is southern Sweden. Seventeenth-century ‘Sweden’ included not only future Finland but also large parts of today’s Baltic Republics and slices of Northern Germany. Differentiation in terms of identity, legal definitions, and institutional arrangements was typical to the processes involved with formation of the state but also, considering the modern period, concerns about the moral improvement of the subjects. Our focus in this paper is how cultural diversity and ideas about modern nationhood and moral improvement reflect in formulaic sequences at administrative level. From an empirical point of view we hold that border regions of different types provide particularly interesting cases with respect to formulaic language. We draw on empirical illustration – petitions and so called five-year reports by local governors – from the 17th- 19th centuries and the Swedish-Danish region of Halland.

Theoretical considerations

The notion of ‘formulaic language’ in terms of analytical tool appears relevant from a historical perspective,¹ e.g. with respect to early-modern state building. Centralization of political power and homogeneity of legal and other institutional arrangements – two key features of the modern state – was preceded by or, as in some cases, went hand in hand with conceptual innovation, linguistic standardization, and new ways to talk and write about politics and statesmanship in diplomatic and legal context. Macchiavelli’s writings is one obvious example,² the development of the English state under Henry VII and Henry VIII is another.³ The Nordic countries from the 16th century onwards represents yet other examples.⁴ However, as was the case e.g. in early-modern Sweden,⁵ different perceptions of ethnic belonging and legal definitions of statehood at the same time with each other, and conceptions of honour, and personal relationships among the nobility blended with emerging state institutions.⁶ From the late 18th and early 19th century onwards, regional variation in terms of culture and ethnicity did however become aligned with the emergence of the modern nation state. Regional attachment evolved into an aspect of citizenship, in some respects similar to the notion of *Heimat* in German context.⁷ Typically, the state also expressed concerns about the social and moral standing of the subjects in connection to this development.

An advantage with ‘formulaic language’, as we understand the concept, relates to the problem of causality and change in historical context: Formulaic language *facilitates* communication rather than determines the societal *outcomes* of communication e.g. in terms of power and domination. Context therefore plays an important although variable role. As Norman Fairclough notes, context implies that different texts ‘within the same chain of events or which are located in relation to the same (network of) social practices, and which represent broadly the same aspects of the world, differ in the discourses upon which they draw’.⁸ In the understanding of Quentin Skinner, context is understood in an even wider sense; rather than being a ‘determinant of what is said’, context should be ‘treated as an ultimate framework for helping to decide what conventionally recognizable meanings /.../ [in a particular society] it might in principle have been possible for someone to have intended to communicate’.⁹

Depending on context, then, formulaic sequences have the potential to facilitate communication and intentions, e.g. between rulers and subjects in early modern society or,

for that matter, between elected representatives and citizens in modern democracies. We suggest that ‘context’ in such cases should be understood in the widest possible sense, and as something depending not only on the social and cultural situation of communication, but also the political and formal, institutional framework. A case in point would be the construction of different administrative levels involved with state building from the early modern period onwards, and the style of communication involved with the interaction between different levels of state administration in connection to this process.

Early modern petitions from the hundreds to parliament

Hallands transition from Denmark to Sweden in 1645 meant that the inhabitants gained access to partially new communication channels. They had been able to communicate with the former Danish central power, but now they got access to new political institutions. Most tangible was representation in the Swedish parliament from 1662 onwards. They also faced, after retaining Danish laws and church ceremonies (including sermon language) from the early 1680s onwards, demands for economical, judicial, political, and linguistic uniformity. The central power wanted them to be *försvenskade* (‘swedificated’).¹⁰

Hypothetically, the incorporation of Halland into the Swedish realm was reflected, among other, in the local petitions submitted by the hundreds (‘häradar’) to the diets from 1660 onwards. In the following, two such petitions – from the hundreds of Hök & Tönnersjö, located in the southern part of Halland (1668) and from Halmstad & Tönnersjö (1765-66) – will be used as illustrations to the role of formulaic sequences in the communication between the local level and state authority. Early modern petitions, with its mostly stereotypical formulations, are undeniably good examples on the use of formulaic language. The documents can be considered ‘written ritual performances’.¹¹ The stereotypical qualities of petitions must however not necessarily be seen as an analytic obstacle. On the contrary, stereotypical formulations can be seen as the result of an interaction between sender and receiver regardless of whether the petitions are individual or collective. The content is “true” in so far it is reasonable and legitimate for the all parties involved.¹² Therefore, petitions are not only written ritual performances but, at the same time, also expressions of ritualized *interaction* between sender and recipient, a construction of, and confrontation between, different types of imaginary worlds.¹³

The petition of 1668 is a four-page document written in Danish and consists of seven items concerning taxes, custom and trade.¹⁴ The formulations are typical to the period. The king is greeted with the phrase; ‘Great Mighty King. Most Gracious Lord!’ whereas the petitioners describe themselves as ‘poor, obliged and humbled subjects’ and as ‘dwellers from small places here in Halland’, ‘affected by war and crop failures’. Their narrative is retrospective and the argument is that their privileges are valid since ancient times (‘av ålders tid, av arilds tid’). Unlike the case in Blekinge, yet another, formerly Danish province, the past is however not identified with any ethnic or cultural notion of ‘Denmark’; in petitions from Blekinge from this period, retrospective phrase such as ‘in the Danish time’, and ‘under the rule of Denmark’ were used.¹⁵ Rather, in Halland the past is communal and local. The only actual reference to the past in this case is a reminder of an agreement between regional representatives of Halland and the Swedish central government dating back to 1648 and concerning, among, other things economical privileges.

By comparison the 1760 petition is written in Swedish and consists of five pages.¹⁶ It addresses one single issue – the privileges granted to the commoners by the town of Halmstad with respect to fishing rights in the river Nissan, and their duty to oblige the burghers with timber products suitable for fishing grounds. The king is addressed with the same phrase as in 1668: ‘Great Mighty King. Most Gracious Lord!’. Similarly, the document is signed by the ‘humble and obliged subject’ Hans Larsson, representative of the commoners (‘allmogen’) in Halmstad and Tönnersjö hundreds to the diet. Single members of the hundreds are referred to as “bonden” (the farmer [in singular]), but as a collective in terms of ‘allmogen’ (commoners) and, more generally, as ‘landets innevånare’ (inhabitants of the countryside) that ‘humbly hopes’ for a positive response: To be released from their duties to the burghers of Halmstad.

However, the past interfered with the request of the petitioners. Attached to the petition is a protocol from a meeting held at Halmstad Castle arranged by the governor of Halland. At the meeting several privileges of Halmstad town from late 15th to early 18th century were listed and recited in the presence of representatives of both the commoners and the burghers. Historically, it appears that the commoners had no case. Instead, they argued with reference to present necessities, i.e. that ‘the forests are nowadays so depleted and there is an urgent need for careful economical use of them (‘kräver noga hushållning’). Also, this situation

could worsen if forest fires took place. This passage directly ties in with the typical, 18th century culture of utility ('nyttokultur'), including, among other things, the idea that there was need for a strict economization in order to strengthen and improve the prosperity of the state and the realm.¹⁷

By way of summary, the two petitions include several examples of formulaic sequences, not least with respect to how regal authority is addressed and, consequently, how the petitioners themselves introduce themselves. The petitions are, at the same time, scribal expressions of the gradual 'swedification' of Halland. In terms of culture and language this is reflected in the shift from Danish to Swedish in the petitions. The texts also reflect changes in terms of the temporal orientation of the petitioners, the new subjects of the emerging Swedish state. In terms of the self-representation and orientation of the petitioners a shift occur from 1668 onwards, from identification by help of looking backward and to past precedence, on to stressing the importance of contemporary and future conditions. Questions that can, for the moment, be left open, concern the actual causes behind linguistic changes such as these. Were they a result of increasing demands on local subjects raised by the early modern state? Or should the texts, perhaps, be considered as parts of a, at least in part, reciprocal dialogue between local interests and central state authority?

At the same time an important similarity should be noted. The king, the embodiment of the state as it were, is addressed similarly throughout the period, a sequence that basically remains the same throughout the 18th and, indeed, the 19th century as well. By that time, state authority and the government structures through which the different provinces were administrated had been standardized. By 1800 Sweden was divided into 24 regions – counties – that were governed by county administrative boards headed by the county governor. The system had been instituted in the 1630s, but e.g. forms of communication, documentation and reporting between different levels of the state apparatus had become standardized only in the 1800s. Local governor's reports are a case in point; in contrast to the petitions presented in the above, a substantial part of the governor's five-years reports are also digitized (1822-1905), a feature that opens up for systematic surveys.

19th century local governor's reports

Swedish governors were, by royal instruction, obliged to summarize the demographic and economic etc conditions and developments in their respective counties, and, as indicated by their name, to submit them to Stockholm every fifth year. Similarly to 17th and eighteenth century petitions, the reports includes examples of formulaic sequences touching on the topic of regional diversity. Presumably, the formulæ intended to facilitate communication and, as part of this process, helped convey images of regional differentiation as well as emerging stereotypes of national identity. Originally, the reports appeared in the 17th century, as an aspect of the efforts to centralize and standardize administration at regional level. Throughout the 17th and 18th centuries, though, submissions of the reports was not systematic, and the texts had a standardized format only during the 1805-1905 period. The five-year reports beginning with the 1817-1822 period, were published and based on information gathered by the county administrative boards. However, from the late 1850s onwards, the reports were compiled by Statistics Sweden (Statistiska Centralbyrån) and other sources were added than those collected by the county administrative board. The last five-year reports dealt with the period 1901-1905. From the point of view of state building, the use of formulaic sequences, and integration of old border regions the reports makes interesting reading.

Considering an old border region such as Halland, e.g. the 1822 report is introduced by help of the exact same phrasing as the report for ‘classic’ Swedish core regions, notably Dalarna (Stora Kopparberg county) – they are, as a mirror image of the period, ‘humble accounts’, addressed to his royal highness the king; we should note the similarity between this type of colocation and the expression ‘humble subjects’ in the petitions previously presented. The formulæ ‘humble account’ was used throughout the 19th century and, in the case of the reports, it presumably signals and clarifies the position of the governor as a *mediator* between the subjects and the ruler. The king, though, ruled over a rather motley collection of peoples, as much is clear from a comparison of the reports – just as he had in the 17th century.

According to the 1822 report for Halland, the level of morality among the locals is ‘commendable’, whereas among the people of Dalarna, the report for this particular county stress that ‘old customs and earnest, Swedish manners’ has been preserved there, better compared to in other parts of the country.¹⁸

The kind of formalized communication indicated in the above obviously draw on descriptions in the form of stereotypes, and, as we shall be able to observe, even caricatures and pseudoscientific characteristics. But whereas the petitions of the 17th and 18th centuries illustrates above all the emerging economic and fiscal bonds by which the subjects were tied

to the emerging state, the 19th-century five-year reports outlines moral social characteristics of the Swedish nation, and the attempts of local state authority to improve it; because, as it turns out, not all subjects in Halland were of good standing and commendable morality, according to the state. As illustration to this we draw on an additional three five-year reports for Halland, for the 1827-31, 1832-36, and 1837-42 periods.

In the 1827-31 report, the local population is described mainly in terms of three, different groups: rural commoners (peasants), the servant class, and sons and farmhands of the peasantry.¹⁹ These are exclusively groups without much social standing. However, in line with the very first report from the early 1820s, the behavior of each group remains by and large good – these subjects are said to possess an education and morality that are acceptable – the ‘people’s temperament’ as a whole is simply praiseworthy’. However, with respect to the sons of the peasantry and the farmhands, these were, by contrast, taking every opportunity to ‘pass the whole day [...] in idleness while consuming booze and gambling’, according to the report.

Social behavior – sobriety and drunkenness alike – is considered due mainly due to external factors and measures. The story points out that expressions of sobriety and good manners is, ultimately, an effect of poor harvests and crop failures; these have resulted in rising prices for alcohol and, consequently, that people simply cannot afford to drink as much as usual. The fact that the number of countryside inns, where alcohol is usually served, has also dwindled because of the closing down of transport routes. In addition, as a means to promote ‘sobriety and moral conduct, several parishes in Halland had also decided on a ‘sparse distribution of spirits at weddings, baptisms and burials.’ The good conduct of the people, then, is more the result of crop failures, prohibitions, and withdrawals than of intrinsic personal qualities. Behavior is largely regulated by societal solutions controlled from above. Such external control is necessary because personal agency cannot be trusted, especially considering the lower strata of society.

A similar pattern can be identified in the 1832-36 report.²⁰ As in the previous report, it focus the lower strata of society. Drinking was, again, identified as a problem and an indication of the individual not being in full control of his or her behavior. Paternalist care and control was therefore seen as the solution. Similarly to the previous report, it says that ‘weaker harvests and crop failures probably contributed to sobriety among the peasantry.’ We recognize the formulae from the previous report, but failing harvests cannot stop a large increase in

population. This increase was worrying and ‘by no means satisfactory to the general welfare’. In some parishes in the county, the landless groups of crofters and cottagers with families could amount to almost a third of the population. In the report, large families are seen as problematic and in need of paternalistic guidance on the need for sexual restraint and family planning. This lack of self-control, according to the narrative of the report, has ‘put the latter in poverty while increasing begging. A difference in relation to the previous report, though, is the terminology used to describe different groups of the population. Compared to the 1827-31 report, two new categories enter the narrative about the lower strata of local society: crofters and cottagers (‘backstugesittare’). Indeed, a similar pattern is typical to the next report as well, concerning the 1837-42 period: Whereas the moral standing of the subjects is expressed in the same, stereotypical terminology, the actual groups included in the assessment differ somewhat – or do they..? Because, in the 1837-42 report the terminology changes again. This time categories such as ‘slaves’ (!), ‘independents’, and ‘the arbitrary’ are applied. It remains an open question whether the kind of different expressions and categories that were used in the above actually referred to different population groups (considering the societal changes in the 19th century), or whether different, standardized categories were ‘tested’ to describe basically one and the same social strata. It appears, that the overall notion of ‘morality’ could be used both as a means to pass judgement – but also that formulæ containing, or alluding to ‘morality’ at the same time was an established means to facilitate the moral improvement of specific groups of people and socioeconomic strata. The Swedish nation, such as in the case of the old border region of Halland, was taken measure of, by authority, and not only in pure numbers, to speak with Benedict Anderson.²¹

Concluding remarks

A final note relating to DH and data extraction should be included. At least the above-mentioned governor’s five-year reports are digitized and available through Statistics Sweden in searchable PFD-format for the 1817-1905 period (260 reports). Digitizing that would allow for data extraction would however require the application of software such as Transkribus et al. platforms. Also, worth noticing are classic, historiographical issues, relating in particular to the governor’s reports in terms of historical sources. The reports followed a certain template. Furthermore, we should not exclude the possibility that various expressions and statements in the material were, in effect, systematically copied from report to report. For

example, Per Hammarström has used the material to uncover stereotypes about Jews in 19th-century Sweden, but it is not clear to which extent such stereotypes reflected contemporaneous discourses about Jews and Jewishness, or whether the expressions are, at least in part, an effect of the sources themselves.²² For the purpose of the present conference circumstances such as this presents the analysts with problems as well as opportunities. On the one hand, stereotypes as an effect of historical sources, for example as in official documents and reports, is potentially of great value for the study of formulaic language in historical context. On the other hand, careful use of the sources and the information that they provide of formulaic language is necessary if the purpose is to reconstruct everyday discourses on topics such as ethnic, regional and other possible expressions of identification.

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¹ Among other Webb, 'Classifying and Identifying Formulaic Language'.

² Viroli, *From Politics to Reason of State*.

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⁴ Gustafsson, *Gamla riken, nya stater*.

⁵ Lerbom, *Svenskhetens tidigmoderna gränser*.

⁶ Thorelli, *De tjänstvilliga vännernas samhälle*.

⁷ Fransson, *Landskapet som lärobok*.

⁸ Fairclough, *Analysing discourse*, 127.

⁹ Skinner, 'Meaning and understanding in the history of ideas', 49.

¹⁰ Lerbom, 'Mellan två riken – Halland i fred och ofred'.

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